

ISic3714

I.Sicily inscription 3714

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication (?)

Material

marble ('rosato')

Object

fragment

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Agrigentum

Place of origin (modern)

Agrigento

Provenance

?from excavations of ekklesiastikon, S.Nicola?

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Agrigento, Museo Regionale
Archeologico Pietro Griffo, inventory 8330

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR136025

1. [---]A [---]
2. [---] ἔδωκε [---]
3. [---]ιδει
- 4.

Edition: PHI336050

1. [— — — — — — — — —]
2. [— — —]A I [— — — — —]
3. [— — —] ἔδωκε [— — —]
4. [— — —]ιδει.
- 5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

EDR 136025

PHI 336050

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 49.1266.6

Manganaro, G. 1999. Sikelika: studi di antichità e di epigrafia della Sicilia greca. Pisa, Roma. At 36 no.6 fig.83

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3714. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4389031>